

NAVIGATING GENDER DYNAMICS IN STEM: CHALLENGES, PROGRESS, AND THE PATH FORWARD

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The field of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) has long been dominated by men, but the past few decades have seen a gradual shift towards inclusivity. The increasing participation of women in STEM is not only a testament to their capabilities but also a catalyst for innovation and progress. However, the journey for women in STEM is not without its challenges and barriers.

Gender stereotypes are part of a broader belief system that includes attitudes toward female and male family roles, female and male occupations, and gender-associated perceptions of the self.

Extensive research has thoroughly examined the contrasts between the binary constructs of males and females. Across many domains, men both out- (over-) and underperform women; there is little evidence of average difference in intelligence. Men prefer working with things; women prefer working with people. Men have more "investigative" interests; women have more "artistic" and "social" interests. Men are also, on average, more interested in math, science and engineering.

Historically, women have been underrepresented in STEM fields due to societal norms and gender stereotypes, that perpetuate the notion that certain subjects are more suitable for men, while others are better suited for women, thus discouraging women from pursuing careers in STEM.

The 20th century witnessed significant advancements in gender equality, with women gaining access to education and employment opportunities.

With respect to the overall gender equality, depending on the chosen metrics, Latvia is deemed an average-to top performer. According to the Gender Gap Index 2023, Latvia ranks among the top countries, sharing the index of the same value with countries like Ireland, Belgium, United Kingdom. The leaders of the Index are Scandinavian countries. With respect to female researchers as a percentage of total researchers -Latvia is also a top-performer boasting the 2nd place in Europe – 52,2%.

The data indicates progress towards gender equality, yet the extent to which this reflects genuine parity or is influenced by country-specific factors remains uncertain. In Latvia, for instance, the relatively low investment in R&D may contribute to the success in fostering women's participation in science.

When addressing the issue of equality, we have often approached it superficially, perhaps inadvertently ignoring its underlying complexity. The dominance of men in decision-making roles may have led to a skewed interpretation of "equality for women," often framed within the parameters of male perspectives and definitions of success.

In Latvia, women have nearly equal opportunities as men for full-time employment. However, they also bear a disproportionate burden of household responsibilities. The author contends that in Latvia's efforts to promote gender equality, the unintended consequence has been the imposition of additional burdens on women. This has inadvertently added to women's challenges in balancing personal and professional duties, often at the expense of competing effectively in the male-dominated sphere.

Rather than evaluating women's contributions solely based on male-centric standards, what is imperative is engaging in an open dialogue that fosters an overarching transformation in societal norms and expectations. This shift is essential to acknowledge and appreciate the multifaceted contributions of both genders.

Women need to be more vocal and assertive about defining what success looks like for them, prompting a broader reevaluation of traditional gender roles and stereotypes. This approach transcends mere advocacy for a fairer distribution of responsibilities within existing structures, advocating instead for a fundamental shift in how we perceive and accommodate gender dynamics.

While promoting shared responsibilities and breaking barriers for women's access to education, employment, and leadership is crucial, achieving true gender equality requires more. We need to cultivate an environment where individuals can pursue their aspirations without gender constraints. This involves implementing policies and cultural attitudes supporting work-life balance for everyone, acknowledging the importance of unpaid work typically performed by women.

One would imagine that countries, treating women equally, would provide the best options for women to excel in STEM. However, recent research has shown that countries with greatest "gender equality" (like in Scandinavia) have some of the largest STEM gaps, leading to the contradictory conclusion that, when women are free to choose, they choose STEM less often.

Given the undeniable imperative for increased involvement of the population in STEM disciplines, when conveying the necessity for women's participation in STEM, we must move away from the rational and male-centric approach of simply stating "we need more women in STEM." Instead, we should adopt communication methods that better resonate with females, emphasizing the inherent value and benefits of joining the STEM community as scientists.

In addition to the inherent inability of males to fully understand the experiences of females, the absence of women in STEM has contributed to a research landscape that is predominantly male-centered.

This imbalance has resulted in concerning outcomes, such as 70% of drugs withdrawn from the market are presenting greater health risks for women, women face a greater risk of developing adverse reactions to drugs compared to men, women are overdosed, gender differences have been observed in the effectiveness of treatments. These discrepancies, among other, underscore the importance of pursuing gender diversity in research.

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